

Deterioration and Chemical Preservation to the Ancient Structure - Elephant Statue (Protected Monument), Ariyalur, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

Elephant Statue is a protected monument at Elayaperumalnallur Village in Udayarpalayam Taluk of Ariyalur District, Tamil Nadu. The selected coordinates i.e. Latitude 11°14'51.2"N, longitude: 79°26'45.4"E is found within the limit of Elayaperumalnallur Village. A state in southeast India is a sizable masonry construction made of tiles, mud, lime surkhi mortar, and terracotta bricks. The monuments have been let to deteriorate over many centuries. Monuments are constantly deteriorating because to environmental changes and extended periods of exposure. Along with a scientific approach to monument preservation, this article discusses significant weathering and degrading factors such as temperature, relative humidity, atmosphere, rainwater, surface water, ground water, biological growth, and human vandalism. Significant efforts have been taken to ensure that this kind of monument protection is both weather resistant and beneficial to the monuments' overall health.

KeyWords - Elephant Statue, Ancient structure, Bricks, Lime mortar, Deterioration, Preservation, Archaeology, Degradation, Microorganism, Stucco.

I. Introduction

The degradation of brick structures and the weathering of monuments may be greatly impacted by atmospheric pollution, often known as air pollution. A summary of the analytical methods used to evaluate the deterioration processes will be provided, along with a discussion of the key weathering mechanisms. There is also discussion of how tourism affects the preservation of masonry structures. Of fact, air pollution also has a negative impact on a variety of priceless and frequently irreplaceable cultural heritage objects, with varying degrees of severity, susceptibility, and repair costs. It is only lately that scientific interest in the preservation of our cultural heritage and safeguarding it from potential harm caused by outdoor air pollution has increased.

Bricks to be treated with red oxide solution after a thorough examination of the building, applying the solution methodically, and sprayed in two layers on clean, dry surfaces. A thin mist

of water should be sprayed after application to expedite the reaction. The treated surface should be completely dried after the oxidation process is complete before scaling or cleaning [1].

Historical monuments are man-made locations with over a century of historical, cultural, religious, or architectural significance. Various biological and artificial raw materials, including mud, stones, bricks (terracotta), lime surkhi plaster, mortar, and tiles, were used to create different kinds of monuments. Thus, a variety of elements, including the environment, pollution, biology, mechanical systems, and chemicals, can cause building materials to deteriorate. [2] Thousands of visitors from both domestic and other countries visit these monuments. Moreover, it provides details about the history of the state, the nation, and notable individuals. Therefore, it is imperative that they are preserved and conserved. This section explains the preservation and chemical conservation efforts for the protected monuments located in the Ariyalur region of Tamilnadu. Bricks, lime surkhi mortar, and lime surkhi plaster were used to construct the elephant statue. For ages, even millennia, the monuments made of bricks, lime, and surkhi have been left to deteriorate.

The monuments are always deteriorating because to the extended periods of exposure and environmental changes. Monument deterioration is mostly caused by environmental causes, pollution, biological conditions, chemical reactions, human vandalism, etc. [3,4].

The amount of pollutants in the air that are carried by rain and surface waters is changing due to the increased rate of air pollution in urban and industrial areas brought on by the burning of fossil fuels. The usage of the monuments affects their state and is a major factor in their degradation. It was very important to clarify the monument's preservation status and environmental circumstances using this item. As a result, we discussed scientific conservation and preservation against weathering in this work.

To preserve and conserve the fort, investments should be made in replacing or repairing deteriorating structural parts or masonry, controlling vegetation to reduce damage, and ensuring regular maintenance. A public outreach or volunteer program could also be created to involve individuals in the upkeep and preservation of the fort. Regular inspections are also necessary to ensure the fort's safety and remove any structural or cosmetic alterations [5].

The conservation team suggested adding a buoyancy chamber to the church's basement to allow water to flow out. To improve structural integrity, routine inspections, cleaning, and stabilization techniques were implemented. Conventional lime pointing and non-invasive conservation methods were used to maintain the current finish. A conservation handbook was created to educate people about the importance of safeguarding historic buildings [6].

Bati et al [7]. conducted experimental studies on bricks, examining their compressive strength, water temperature, and mechanical properties. They suggested using a universal compression test to better understand heat-resistant materials like brick. They also compared laboratory testing results with industrial manufacturing results, discussed the impact of chemical additions on brick mechanical characteristics, and discussed the advantages and disadvantages of steel mesh reinforcement.

The Danish Fort of Tranquebar needs a multidisciplinary approach, including archaeological investigations, long-term assessment, and conservation planning. The integration of existing structures and a research team will monitor and apply necessary therapies. This comprehensive approach, involving consultation with experts from various fields, is crucial for preserving the historic structure [8].

The research focuses on preserving historic structures like bridges by addressing environmental issues like weathering and erosion. It suggests protective coatings, maintenance, community involvement, stakeholder collaboration, regulations, infrastructure investment, and long-term conservation strategies for culturally important objects [10].

The Manora Fort in Thanjavur is a tourist attraction and historical research site, offering valuable resources for researchers and students. It hosts educational activities and seminars to promote tourism and preserve Thanjavur's heritage. The fort, built using lime mortar, features water-resistant and fire-resistant construction, making it an excellent opportunity for heritage tourism and providing valuable resources for academics and researchers [14].

The Giant Granary in Tamil Nadu, a historic landmark, has been restored using traditional lime mortar for sustainable architecture. The building is well-ventilated and temperature-controlled, providing insulation and low shrink rate. However, further conservation work is needed to assess water damage, implement corrosion protection systems, monitor the structure, and use modern materials in accordance with conservation principles [17].

The decay of Sibsagar monuments is primarily caused by factors like temperature, humidity, atmosphere, rain water, biological growth, human vandalism, and bird effects. Scientific preservation offers weather resistance and maintains the monuments' breathing, thereby preventing harmful agents from deteriorating [18].

The following significant weathering and deteriorating factors are Wind patterns, relative humidity, Cloud Cover, Natural Precipitation, Subsurface Water, Biological Growth, Vandalism caused by human beings, Influence of Birds etc.

Climatic conditions :-

(a) Wind patterns

The average wind speed in Elayaperumalnallur is 3.1 m/s with the maximum wind speed of around 10 m/s. The average ambient temperature remains 30°C, varies from 24°C to 36°C. The average relative humidity remains around 73.3%, varies from 29.3% to 98.8%. The station pressure varies from 995 hPa to 987 hPa, averaged around 1004 hPa. Windrose of Elayaperumalnallur Village, Ariyalur shows that predominantly wind blow from the WSW - about 13.63% of all wind directions. (Fig.1)

Fig 1. The annual wind rose below showing how wind speed and direction are typically distributed

Table of Frequencies (%)

Direction	< 0.5	0.5-1.0	1.0-2.0	2.0-3.0	3.0-4.0	4.0-5.0	> 5.0	Total
N	0.03	0.07	0.99	1.13	0.41	0.41	0.24	3.28
NNE	0.10	0.27	1.99	4.25	2.43	1.10	0.38	10.52
NE	0.00	0.03	1.78	5.44	3.29	2.12	0.68	13.34
ENE	0.07	0.10	1.85	4.69	2.81	1.88	0.27	11.67
E	0.00	0.31	1.03	2.53	1.40	0.48	0.07	5.82
ESE	0.03	0.07	1.40	1.34	0.92	0.07	0.00	3.83
SE	0.00	0.14	1.54	2.23	0.89	0.03	0.00	4.83
SSE	0.07	0.27	1.47	2.57	0.96	0.07	0.03	5.44
S	0.00	0.17	1.23	1.99	0.82	0.03	0.00	4.24
SSW	0.03	0.24	1.54	1.57	0.34	0.10	0.03	3.85
SW	0.10	0.21	1.23	1.57	0.51	0.17	0.214	3.93
WSW	0.07	0.10	1.37	2.98	2.81	2.91	3.39	13.63
W	0.03	0.21	0.68	1.92	2.19	3.12	5.03	13.18
WNW	0.00	0.07	0.24	0.21	0.41	0.31	0.17	1.41
NW	0.00	0.07	0.21	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.34
NNW	0.00	0.07	0.38	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.65
Total	0.53	2.40	18.93	34.55	20.32	12.80	10.43	100

Table 1. This table shows the frequency and speed of wind blowing from each direction

Graph 1. The graph below shows the minimum, maximum and average wind speed, m/s

(b) Relative Humidity

The average Relative Humidity of Ariyalur is around 73% although it vary from around 65% during Monsoon (August) to 82% during the Post-Monsoon (October). The most humid month of the year is October with humidity varies from 45.2% to 98.2%. The least humid month is of the year is August, with humidity varies from 35.9% to 93.8%. (Table 2)

Graph 2. The graph below shows the minimum, maximum and average % Relative Humidity

Parameter	Relative Humidity, %			Standard Deviation
	Minimum	Maximum	Average	
January	44.0	97.7	73.2	± 14.5
February	39.3	96.6	72.8	± 16.5
March	37.0	97.3	73.5	± 17.6
April	41.3	97.3	74.2	± 15.7
May	44.0	97.5	74.9	± 13.4
June	37.5	96.6	70.0	± 13.2
July	36.7	95.1	65.5	± 13.2
August	35.9	93.8	65.2	± 13.9
September	29.3	96.6	69.2	± 16.4
October	45.2	98.2	81.8	± 13.0
November	42.0	98.8	81.6	± 13.0
December	44.2	97.0	78.1	± 13.0

Table 2. The table below shows the minimum, maximum and average % Relative Humidity

(c) Cloud Cover

The average Cloud Cover is around 6/10th although it vary from around 2/10th during Winter (February) to 9/10th during the Monsoon (August). The most cloudy month of the year is August with cloud cover varies from 2/10th to 10/10th. The most clear sky month is of the year is February, with cloud cover varies from 0/10th to 10/10th. (Table 3)

Graph 3. The graph below shows the minimum, maximum and average Cloud Cover

Parameter	Cloud Cover, /10 th			Standard Deviation
	Minimum	Maximum	Average	
January	0.0	10.0	3.9	± 3.5
February	0.0	9.9	2.5	± 2.6
March	0.0	10.0	3.8	± 3.4
April	0.0	10.0	3.5	± 3.3
May	0.1	10.0	7.0	± 3.1
June	1.3	10.0	8.9	± 1.7
July	1.9	10.0	8.8	± 1.9
August	2.4	10.0	9.4	± 1.1
September	0.5	10.0	7.5	± 2.9
October	1.9	10.0	8.1	± 2.1
November	0.0	10.0	7.0	± 3.2
December	0.0	10.0	7.1	± 2.9

Table 3. The table below shows the minimum, maximum and average Cloud Cover

Table 4. The table below shows the minimum, maximum and average cloud cover, 10th

(d) Natural Precipitation

The south-eastern area experiences year-round high rainfall. The monument's location in the south-east (Ariyalur District) has a rainfall distribution pattern [9] that includes periods of heavy rain from September to November, with December marking the commencement of the rainy season. In the Ariyalur District, the excessive rainfall has led to the thick and opulent development of flora. The monuments exhibit expansion during the rainy season and constriction during the dry season. The enormous surface of the monuments is caused by the growth of macro- and micro-vegetation, which also gives the monument an inappropriate appearance and accelerates its degradation. Rainwater's composition and the atmosphere's composition are closely related. Rainwater has a pH between 6.7 and 7.5.

(e) Subsurface Water

Deeper foundations and sporadic direct contact with ground water are potential problems for monuments. Groundwater preservation is still crucial, but not for the in-situ preservation of archaeological sites. When combined with hydrological forces and soil's propensity to absorb moisture horizontally [11], high moisture levels—which may be observed in Ariyalur because of the proximity of a sizable pond at the monuments baseline, the Vellar and Cauvery River basins—become problematic. It is often acknowledged that the water is a building's feud. Despite the fact that the monument's exterior and baseline seem to be always wet throughout the rainy season, this might be due to elevated groundwater levels.

(f) Biological Growth

Lichens, algae and fungus have a symbiotic interaction that has a significant impact on the surface of monuments. Though more typically destructive, they are said to be protective at times. Lichens are the first symbiotic organisms to generate humus, which subsequently sustains higher plants. Their sluggish development and capacity to adhere to building surfaces without the assistance of soil characterise their symbiotic system [3]. They are destroying the monuments' aesthetic value and adding a rough surface to the crumbling stonework. Damage in

the future might result from the rough surface and spongy nature of the lichens, algae, and fungus, which hold water for a while and keep the monument's surface moist underneath. H+ cation is produced in very minute amounts by the rhizomes of lichens, algae, and fungi, as well as the roots of higher plants [12]. Negatively charged nutrients may be readily exchanged, and this process is crucial for the dissolution of minerals. The production of complex organic acids from the organic residues, such as humus and carbonic acid, greatly accelerates the break-up process once it has begun. The acid-interacting clay keeps attacking the unweathered materials underneath as long as a layer of colloidal-size clay has formed on the surface [13].

(g) Vandalism caused by human beings

Numerous issues with conservation and preservation are also brought on by human vandalism. On the surface of monuments, human activity frequently results in permanent alterations. These alterations result in structural deterioration in addition to affecting monuments' aesthetic value [15].

(h) Influence of Birds

Birds have a significant impact on Elephant Statue. Because pigeon faeces is deposited on monuments, birds especially pigeons—significantly harm them in terms of chemical and aesthetic elements. Pigeon poop is a great growing medium for microorganisms that are chemoorganotrophic. These microorganisms release acid metabolites, which corrode masonry structures buildings.

II. Brief History and Description

The structure was constructed using brick and lime mortar, the elephant statue stands as one of the largest in Tamil Nadu. It is 8.5 metres tall and is most likely from the 16th or 17th century CE. On a platform that has been fashioned into a rectangle, the elephant is standing majesty. To exert pressure on one of the thief's legs that is visible in front of the elephant, the elephant's right front leg is slightly elevated. The thief's body is seen to be coiling around the trunk. The elephant has large ears and tusks. The elephant's neck is decked with several chains, one of which has a caparison on its forehead and several bells linked to it. The top of the body is covered with a mat or beautifully adorned material. On either side of the elephant's body, three bells are visible dangling from the chains.

Three nearly life-size standing people have been placed on either side of the opening created by the elephant's front and back legs. Every figure has four arms. The figures on each side of him are carrying the Pasha and the Parashu in their upper arms, while the central figure on the left is most likely holding the Shank and the chakra. The Pasha and the trishula are held in the upper arms of the central figure on the right. While the other figure beside him is clutching a

sword and a shield in his upper arms, the damaru and trishula are held by one of the other characters.

The individuals' lower limbs are shown in various poses or as musical instruments. The elephant's body is supported by a few props that resemble pillars that are placed behind these figures. The elephant's front right leg, the guard dog, and the jack fruit tree are visible next to the thief. The robber is seen with a well-groomed beard and a lengthy moustache. A woman is seen with a pot slung over her hip as she stands just behind the robber.

III. Conservation Hazards

The uncovered areas indicated that the statue was constructed of brick and lime mortar, with the surface coated with thick lime plaster. Over the lime plaster, there is a thin layer of lime mortar mixed with red ochre. It is unclear if this layer was originally there or was added later during the refurbishment or conservation process. Attempts were previously made to replace the parts where the lime mortar had worn away or was absent using cement mortar. Specifically, the platform on which the elephant stands is eventually covered with cement mortar.

The elephant statue has attempted to be cleaned of micro-vegetation development, including lichen, moss, algae, and fungus, as well as attempts to patch any fractures that have formed in the monument's plaster in 2021. A 5% hydrogen peroxide solution is utilised to eradicate the strains brought on by the bird excrement. Using a delicate brush, apply 10% ammonia solution to the statue's surface to eliminate the micro-vegetations. After that, the surface was properly cleaned to ensure that no chemicals remained. To remove the stains on the platform and the statue's exterior, additional solutions of 5% sodium carbonate solution and 5% extran (MA 02 neutral soap solution) are being utilised.

The statue's plaster developed cracks, some of which were found to be more than 2 to 3 mm wide when the cracks were investigated in 2021. On the surface of the statue, many line fractures were also discovered. The reasons of the cracks, however, have not been attempted to be found. Furthermore noted was the widespread deterioration of the lime plaster. In order to restore the original surface, the worn-out areas were filled using a lime mortar mixture mixed with red ochre. A 2–5% solution of Poly Vinyl Acetate (PVA) was injected into Toluene to fill up the minor fractures. There was some writing, mostly near the base of the elephant statue, in charcoal and other materials. Acetone/toluene has been used to treat them. Following that, the statue's whole surface was treated with a 5–10% solution of sodium silico fluoride acid. The red ochre coating was put all over the statue to preserve its hue from the previous discovery.

The elephant statue is now well preserved. However, a detailed investigation is required to determine the reasons for the statue's crack formation as well as the state of the lime plaster and core components. To find out the specifics about the plaster's constituent and its chemical

and physical characteristics, the lime plaster must be analysed. If at all feasible, the bricks that were used to build the statue must also be examined in a comparable way. The surface of the statue is covered in several locations with mud-nests constructed of mud-wasps and insect homes. Periodic cleaning and examination of the statue were necessary.

The front part of the platform has a heavy layer of oil and soot from the burning of the oil lamps and the burning of the camphor. It can be suggested to the locals to light the camphor and oil lamps a little distance away from the monument. A dwarf wall topped with chain-link fence has adequately enclosed the protected area. Within the enclosed area, a lovely grass has also been created around the monument of the elephant. It has also been planned to irrigate the grass by the installation of an underground conduit that draws water from a nearby source.

IV. Conservation approaches/ Recommendations

(a) Resources and preservation sites

For chemical cleaning, LR grade ammonia solution, LR grade non-ionic liquid detergent (Teepol), and LR grade sodium pentachlorophenate were utilised. Based on silane/silicone, solvent-less silicon concentration is used to treat hydrophobic materials. Various kinds and sizes of paintbrushes and nylon brushes with soft bristles were employed to apply chemicals on the monuments.

(b) Analyze methods

Protected site preservation has required many actions. The first involved superficial dry cleaning, the second involved chemical cleaning using wet chemical techniques, the third involved biocidal treatment to stop the growth of micro- and macrovegetation spores, and the fourth involved hydrophobic treatment to make the monument water resistant.

(c) Superficial Dry Cleaning

The external surfaces of monuments have been superficially cleaned by employing various soft nylon bristle brush types and sizes, paintbrushes, and other necessary tools as needed to eliminate dust, debris, spider webs, pigeon guano (pigeon excreta), macro and micro vegetation growth, etc.

(d) Chemical Sterilization

The affected area should be cleaned of any lichens, algae, fungi, moss, etc. by first soaking it in a solution of 2-3% ammonia mixed with 1-2% non-ionic liquid detergent. Next, using soft nylon bristle brushes of varying sizes and types, carefully scrub the area, depending on the monument's surface condition. Finally, thoroughly wash it with deionized water. The spot that had been cleaned was let to dry before moving on.

(e) Biocidal Therapies

In order to kill and re-arrest the spores of micro and macro vegetation, the cleaned and dried area using wet chemical procedures was treated to a 2-5% aqueous solution of sodium pentachlorophenate. This treatment was repeated after a gap of approximately one week. The area treated with biocide remained totally dry for the following step.

V. Results and Interactions

The effects of the environment and the year's intense rains caused the Elephant Statue (monument) to suffer from a number of deteriorating issues. It had an impact on the building materials as well as the monuments' aesthetic worth. Therefore, chemical treatment and preservation were necessary to reduce these issues and the need for intervention since degraded materials increase the surface porosity of the monument and lengthen the duration that water is retained, both of which accelerate the pace of degradation. The best outcomes are obtained when monuments are treated scientifically and preserved (Fig. 2).

Monuments that have undergone treatment retain their aesthetic value while also having less of an impact on the surrounding environment. Our method of scientific preservation is based on cleaning with moist chemicals. The cleaning chemicals that are employed include liquid ammonia, non-ionic liquid detergent, and deionized water. Sodium pentachlorophenate is employed as a biocidal in this therapy. The good results of the monument surface are demonstrated by the silicone-based Silane/siloxane water repellent (Fig 3). As a result of scientific treatment and preservation, the monuments' surface is completely waterproof and prevents micro- and macro-vegetation spores from growing again. As a result, in addition to providing a long life for the current generation, the monument will also educate future generations about our amazing past and historical study and research.

Before Conservation

After Conservation

Fig 3. Monuments treated scientifically and preserved (Left Side View)

(a) Impact of Liquid ammonia and non-ionic liquid disinfectants

The surface of the monument was covered with both macro and micro plant growth. When moisture and nutrient-rich substrate are present, pigeon guano accelerates the development of plants. Additionally, air pollution was being embedded in the surface of the monument (Fig. 2,3). Acids are created by the aforementioned living and non-living materials. The binding components of monuments disintegrate when acid is produced by the rhizomes of plant growth. When binding components dissolve, degradation processes begin, and they are difficult to halt. During the rainy season, excessive rainfall speeds up this process. The introductory heading provided an explanation of the impact of rainfall. It is quite difficult to remove roots, hyphae, lichens, algae, and fungi from within the monument surface. Because of the neutralisation process, they are softened with mild alkaline water. Rhizomes of macro- and micro-vegetation on monument surfaces create acids. Ammonia is the most practical weak alkali that evaporates quickly. Some alkali are excessively potent and difficult to remove. Because of our scientific approach to minimal loss and maximum production, it was chosen to employ ammonia as a neutralising agent. A mixture of 1-2% non-ionic liquid detergent and ammonia (2–5%) in aqueous solution was utilised. This aqueous ammonical solution softens the root, facilitating the growth's easy removal. Using soft bristle nylon brushes, carefully wash the monument's surface with a 1-2% aqueous solution of non-ionic liquid detergent after making sure all vegetative growth has been removed. The electrically neutral cleaning chemicals in the non-ionic liquid detergent don't include soluble salts or aid in their creation. Non-ionic liquid detergent effectively facilitates the removal of accretion by better wetting the monument's surface. Therefore, using non-ionic liquid detergent is recommended. Following this procedure,

the monuments were completely cleaned using de-ionized water to remove any leftover detergent, hazardous residue, and ammonical substrate.

(b) Impact of silicon based Silane/ Siloxane

Following scientific wet chemical cleaning, the monument surfaces are kept dry and clean for the subsequent step of treatment; however, even after cleaning, microspores remain in the deep surface and travel by air, via the faces of birds, to the monument surface, where they find a suitable environment and grow up [16]. The monuments' surfaces remained totally dry following the biocidal treatment, preventing any further activity. Water-repellent compounds are really utilised to hydrophobically treat the surface of monuments using silicone-based silane/siloxane. The end result of almost all water-repellent chemicals used to hydrophobically treat stone is silicone resin coatings. interacts with the pore water in the substrate or the moisture in the air after application to produce the active component and release alcohol. The active component significantly reduces the substrate's water absorbency. Because there are no blocked pores or capillaries, the substrate nevertheless has a relatively high level of water vapour permeability. Silane/siloxane serves as an excellent water proofing agent and consolidates the item, making it appear to be in a good preservation state. The outcomes were reliable and fulfilling (Fig. 4).

VI. Conclusions

As was previously mentioned, the following are the main causes of the Elephant Statue's deterioration at Elayaperumalnallur Village, a protected monument: natural precipitation, subsurface water, growth of living things, human vandalism, influence of birds, wind patterns, cloud cover, etc. Scientific monument preservation reduces failing elements and strengthens the building materials for futuristic architecture. The outcomes show how much more weather resistant and significant this method of monument protection was. The monuments' capacity to breathe was preserved during treatment, and the permeability of the water vapours remained unchanged. These findings imply that this strategy is beneficial for protecting the monuments' integrity from the damaging agents' rate of degradation.

VII. References

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